

Relationship Between Parenting Styles and Academic Performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Benue State

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Abstract

This study investigated the relationship between parenting styles and academic performance of senior secondary school students in Benue state, Nigeria. The study examined two parental variables namely: authoritative and neglectful. Academic performance indicators explored include: communication skills and creative skills respectively. Two hypotheses guided the study. Correlation design and regression analysis were adopted for the study. The sample size of the study is made up of 396 respondents from a population of 40282 using Taro Yamene formular. Two self-structured questionnaires tagged "Parenting Style Questionnaires (PSQ) and Academic Performance Questionnaires" (APQ) were used for data collection. Data collected for the study were analysed using mean scores, standard deviation and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) to answer research question, while regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha levels. The findings of the study revealed that authoritative parenting style correlated positively with academic performance of male and female senior secondary school students while neglectful parenting style correlated negatively with academic performance of male and female students' academic performance in Benue State. Based on the findings, recommendations were made such as parents should adopts, authoritative parenting style due to its positive relationship with academic performance.

Key words: Parenting Style, Academic Performance, Secondary School and Students

Introduction

The Nigerian education has been faced with so many problems; one of such is poor academic performance of students, especially in Senior School Certificate examination. This has been a source of worry to parents, teachers, educators, educational institutions and the Nigerian government (Asikhia,2000). Studies have revealed that low-socio-economic background, such as parents' level of education, income among others, students' cognitive abilities, school related factors and environment of the home or the support given by the parents and other family members could have positive or negative relationship with students' academic performance (Fan, 2001, Gonzalez-Pienda, Nunez, Gonzalez-Pumarieya, Alvarez,

Roces & Garcia 2002). Others are inadequate infrastructure like laboratories, school plant, classroom arrangements, teachers' qualification, teaching and learning materials, availability of guidance and counselling services, parenting styles and many others.

Academic performance relates to academic subjects a child studies in school and the skills the child is expected to master in each (Kathryn (2010). The author also asserts that academic performance refers to excellence in all academic discipline, in a class as well as extra-curricular activities. It includes excellence in sporting behaviour, confidence, communication skills, and others. According to Samina and Almas (2015) academic performance is the combination of various educational outcomes as indicated through various aspects which differ from institution to institution. Academic performance therefore refers to outcomes from students' participation in curricular and extra-curricular activities in academic institutions. Indicators of performance include motivation, study skills, communication skills, creativity, grades, students' working skills, self-reliance amongst others. Academic performance variables that were examined in this study are communication skills and learning skills. This was to ascertain their relationship with students' academic performance among students.

Izundu (2005) identified environmental variables in a home that may have negative or positive influence on learning capabilities of a child. These factors include: parental socio economic status, level of parental supervision, home location, library facility among others. The author also affirms that these variables could have bearing on students' academic performance in the study area. Similarly, research by Harb and El -Shaarawil (2006), indicated that the most important factor with positive relationship with students' performance is competence in English Language. That is, if students have strong communication skills and have grip on English, it increases their performance. However, other factors that could have connection with students' academic performance are inadequate infrastructure like laboratories, school plant, classroom arrangements, teachers' qualification, availability of guidance and counselling services, parenting styles, and many others. Academic performance therefore, can be defined as what an individual has gained or benefited after been introduced to curricular and extra-curricular activities. Students' academic performance can be rated high or low depending on the circumstances surrounding it. Whereas the above actors have been implicated for declining academic performance of secondary students, not much seems to have been detailed on how they cause poor performance. However, relationship between parenting styles and academic performance seem not to have been given much attention, this is the gap the researchers intends to fill.

Parenting styles are complex activities that include much specific behaviour that work together to influence a child (Rodriguez & Crowley 2009) Asiamah (2013) defined parenting styles as the manner in which parents express their beliefs about how to be a good or bad parent by adopting styles of parenting learned from their parents because they do not know what else to do and because they feel that their ways of parenting is the right ways. Parenting styles are way and manner, parents' guide, monitor, nurture and direct the upbringing of their children/wards based on their values, beliefs and cultural background (Yakubu, 2018).

From the above definitions, parenting styles can be defined as unique nurturing pattern adopted by parents to ensure that their children / wards become useful and acceptable members of the community. Parenting styles to a great extent depend on parents and their attitudes. They are also beneficial in understanding complex behaviours associated with the child outcomes. Most times, parenting styles are reflection of the parents' personalities and how they want their children to be. Examples of parenting styles are authoritative, authoritarian, permissive and neglectful. However, in the context of this study authoritative and neglectful were considered. These two parenting styles were employed because they seem to be the most commonly child rearing techniques adopted by parents in the study area. The fundamental

aspect of parenting includes demandingness and responsiveness. Parental demandingness refers to parental behaviours and attitudes to integrate children into the family by demanding maturity in their children, supervising and disciplining their children and showing willingness to control behavioural problems of their children. This also refers to parents' demonstration of strength, endurance and patience in children upbringing. Parental responsiveness on the other hand means the degree to which parents instill independence, self-regulation and self-assertion in their children by agreeing to be cognizant and supportive of their children's interest, needs and demands (Abesha, 2012). However, parental exhibition of concern and warmth towards their children / wards could be referred to as responsiveness.

Studies by Mandara (2006) and Micki (2008) have shown that the parenting styles experienced by children contribute in no small measure to the moulding of the behavioural pattern generally and academic performance in particular. That is to say that parental rearing technique might shape children's behaviour which could in turn have positive or negative bearing on academic performance. However, the most iconic of these studies was that of Baumrind (1967). According to the author, parents should neither be punitive nor aloof. Instead, they should develop rules for their children and be affectionate with them. Nevertheless, the author's parenting styles are meant to describe normal variations in parenting styles not deviant parenting styles such as might be observed in abusive homes. It is assumed that normal parenting revolves around issues of control that may facilitate students' academic performance. Baumrind (2008) identified four parenting styles namely authoritative, authoritarian, permissive and neglectful. But, for the purpose of this study two out of the four parenting styles identified by Baumrind (2008) were investigated since they seem to be the child rearing styles commonly practiced in the study area.

Parenting Styles and Academic Performance

According to Pittman and Chase - Landale (2001) adolescent girls with authoritative mothers showed the best adjustment of all parenting style groups, while girls with disengaged (neglectful) mothers showed the worst adjustment of all parenting style groups as relate to academic performance. The authors went further to say that those girls whose mothers are authoritative showed better fit with school and perform better academically. The authors also stated that girls who grew up with parents who are negligent had low score which is an indicator of academic performance. Also, Syahidah, Nabeela and Chin (2007) revealed that male and female students of authoritative parents exhibit positive attitude towards leisure reading an indicator of academic performance. It was also observed that the relationship between authoritative parenting style and children's academic performance was having the highest link. Syahidah, Nabeela and Chin (2007), however, revealed that there is no significant difference was found in academic performance of males and females owing to differing parental styles. This means that when parents are democratic in their rearing styles the gap between the academic performance of males and females could be reduced significantly.

Similarly, Ogunleye, Omirin and Balogun (2013) indicated that there was no significant difference in the academic performance of male and female students in relation to authoritative parenting style. In the same vein, Nyarko (2011) reported that there was a significant positive relationship between mothers' authoritativeness and students' school grades academic outcome. This is to say that authoritative parenting style is favourable to both sexes in term of academic outcomes. Correspondingly; Reaney, Denton and West (2002) found that demandingness appears to be less critical to girls than boys in terms of academic outcome. Likewise, Raimi and Adeoye (2002), Pomerentz, Ellen and Jill (2002) and Fennema (2000) asserted that no significant difference exists any longer between male and female academic outcomes in English language especially in secondary schools. In like manner, Conrade and Ho (2001), Lee, Daniels and Kissinger (2006) found that, girls were affected both positively and negatively by parenting style differences among parents while in others boys were more negatively or positively affected by parenting

styles as regard academic performance. In the same vein, Bronte-Tinkew, Moore and Carrano (2006) found that fathers' emotional responsiveness was more highly related to children's performance. From the review it was found that authoritative parenting style correlates positively with female students' academic performance compared to neglectful parenting style. However, this present study examined the relationship between parenting styles and academic of students in relation to gender in the study area.

Statement of the Problem

Stakeholders in education especially teachers, researchers, government, and parents have expressed worries over the poor performance of secondary school students in external examination in Benue state. For instance, 2014 statistics from the West Africa Examination Council from Benue State of Nigeria revealed that out of 61,133 candidates who sat for the examination in the state only 13,735 passed, while 47,398 candidates failed, representing 26.85% versus 73.85 (West African Examination Council, 2014). The above result from the state is quite frustrating and depict poor academic performance and a thing of concern to the researchers as it might threaten the quality of secondary education which is supposed to be the bedrock for further education if nothing urgent is done to address the unwholesome scenario. However, the above scenario is no doubt worrisome, as it is problematic, thus, effecting the gross development of students. The question then arises as to whether parents are actually playing their roles of inculcating good reading habits to their wards or exhibiting the right parenting styles, yet failure in academic studies skyrocket on daily basis.

From the foregoing, it was observed by the researchers through literature that much work has not been done on relationship between parenting styles and students' academic performance in relation to gender. It is this gap that the present study strives to fill. It is against this backdrop that the study examined the relationship between parenting styles and academic performance of Senior Secondary School students in Benue state, Nigeria.

Purpose of the study

The major purpose of this study was to determine the relationship between parenting styles and academic performance of senior secondary school students in Benue State in relation to gender. Specifically, the objectives include to:

1. Determine the relationship between authoritative parenting style and academic performance of male and female students.
2. Investigate the relationship between neglectful parenting style and academic performance of male and female students in the study area.

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship in academic performance of male and female students brought up by authoritative parents.
2. There is no significant relationship in academic performance of male and female students raised under neglectful parenting style.

Methodology

This study adopted correlation survey design. The area of study is Benue State The sample size of the study is made up of 396 students selected from five local government areas in the study area namely Makurdi, Guma, Gwer, Ohimini and Otukpo.

Instruments tagged "Parenting Styles Questionnaire (PSQ) and Academic Performance Questionnaire (APQ) were used to gather data for this study. The PSQ was structured to measure students' views about their parents monitoring techniques while, the APQ was used to measure academic

performance based on performance indices. The PSQ consists of two sections, A and B. Section A contains information on the respondents' bio data, while Section B is sub- divided into two clusters, Cluster A consists of items 3 to 12 on the variables of Authoritative parenting style while Cluster B is made up of items 13 to 22 on the indices of neglectful parenting style. The APQ consists of two sections A and B. Section A contains information on bio data while section B consists of 8 items on indices of academic performance. Items 3 to 6 consist of variables of communication skills while Items 7 to 10 comprises of indices of creative skills respectively. For both PSQ and APQ, respondents were required to indicate their level of acceptance or rejection on a four point modified Likert scale as: Strongly Agree (SA)-4, Agree (A)-3, Disagree (D)-2 and Strongly Disagree (SD) - Face and content validation of the instrument was done by three experts, in guidance and counselling, in the Department of Educational Foundations all from Benue State University, Makurdi. The reliability of the instrument was done using Cronbach-Alpha Coefficient.

Results

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between authoritative parenting style and academic performance of male and female students.

Table 1: Multiple regression analysis of relationship between authoritative parenting style and academic performance of male and female students

Predictors	R	R ²	Df	F	B	(t)	P
Constant	.080	.003	1,394	4.121		93.865	.000
Gender					-0.60	-1.720	.043

The result from Table 10 showed significant relationship between authoritative parenting style and academic performance of male and female students [$R=.080$, $R^2=.003$, $F(1, 394) = 4.121$; $p < .05$]. The result showed that authoritative parenting style accounted for 0.3% of the total variance in academic performance of male and female students. Therefore, the remaining (99.7%) could be accounted for by other variables not entered in the present study. The result also indicated that, authoritative parenting style has positive relationship with academic performance of male and female students ($\beta = -0.60$, $t = -1.720$, $p < .05$).

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between academic performance of male and female students raised under neglectful parenting style.

Table 2: Regression analysis of relationship in academic performance of male and female students raised under neglectful parenting style

Predictors	R	R ²	Df	F	B	(t)	P
Constant	.009	.000	1,394	.311		10.211	.000
Gender					-.001	-.480	.741

The result from Table 16 indicated no significant relationship in academic performance of male and female students raised under neglectful parenting style [$R=.009$, $R^2=.000$, $F(1, 394) = .311$; $p > .05$]. The result showed that neglectful parenting style accounted for 0.0% of the total variance in academic performance of male and female students. Therefore, 100% could be accounted for by other variables not

entered in the present study. The result also revealed that, neglectful parenting style has negative relationship with academic performance of male and female students ($\beta = -.001$, $t = -.480$, $p > .05$).

Discussion

Hypothesis one indicated that there was a significant positive relationship in the academic performance of male and female students brought up by authoritative parents. This is consistent with earlier findings by Pittman and Chase-Landale (2001) that adolescent girls of authoritative mothers showed the best adjustment of all parenting styles group. According to the authors, girls of authoritative mothers showed better fit for school that is they exhibit better academic performance. Similarly, it was revealed by Sarah (2006) that authoritative parenting style had significant positive relationship with girls' grade point average. Similarly, Chan and Chan (2005) found that authoritative parenting style was more effective with females than males in respect of academic performance. This implied that girls of authoritative parents tend to benefit academically than their male counterparts. That is boys tend to perform better academically when raised by undemocratic parents in other word strictness encourages creativity. However, this finding is not in agreement with Steinberg, Blatt-Eisengart and Cauffman (2006) whose finding indicated that there was no gender difference in the relationship between authoritative parenting style and academic performance of male and female students. This is also in agreement with Ogunleye, Omirin and Balogun (2013) who all opined that there was no gender difference in the academic performance of male and female students in relation to authoritative parenting style.

Hypothesis two revealed that there was no significant relationship between the academic performance of male and female students raised by neglectful parents which showed that neglectful parenting style has same bearing on academic performance irrespective of students' gender. This finding tallied with Gracia et al (2008) and Garcia (2009), whose findings portrayed that neglectful parenting style correlated negatively with academic performance of male and female students. This finding is consistent with Zinnatul, Umme, Mahjabeen and Afia (2016) whose study found that neglectful parenting style has negative significant relationship with academic performance of male and female students. This finding disagreed with Pittman and Chase-Landale (2001) whose study revealed that girls of neglectful mothers showed the worst adjustment of all parenting style groups as relate to academic performance.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this research, it was concluded that authoritative parenting style has significant relationship with the academic performance of male and female students in Benue state. However, negative relationship was found between neglectful parenting style and academic performance of male and female students in the study area.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made.

1. Parents should adopt authoritative parenting styles due to its positive relationship with academic performance.
2. Parents should be physically and emotionally present in the lives of their children and wards for higher academic performance in school.

Counselling implications

The results of this study have counselling implications

1. Guidance and counselling units should be set up in all secondary schools. This could enable counsellors to assist students with personal social, vocational and educational challenges that might disrupt high academic performance.
2. Counsellors should assist students to develop coping skills to study and emerge successful irrespective of their parental rearing styles.

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